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**NEW SURGICAL METHOD FOR UMBILICAL HERNIA REPAIR
MAINTAINING NAVEL ANATOMY (ACCORDING TO H.YU.
KHUĐENOV)**

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Umbilical hernias constitute a significant proportion of anterior abdominal wall hernias. Despite the apparent simplicity of surgical treatment, questions remain regarding the preservation of umbilical anatomy, reduction of surgical trauma and recurrences, as well as improvement of cosmetic outcomes. The search for organ-preserving and minimally invasive approaches is of particular relevance. The technique developed by the author makes it possible to achieve these goals through precise, dosed dissection and double plasty of the umbilical ring while preserving the umbilical cord. The advantages of the proposed technique have been analyzed in comparison with traditional methods of hernioplasty [1]; [2]; [3]; [4]; [5]; [6]; [7]; [8]; [9]; [10].

Keywords: umbilical hernia, hernioplasty, navel, anterior abdominal wall, organ-preserving technique, surgical treatment.

Relevance of the Study. Umbilical hernias constitute a significant proportion of anterior abdominal wall defects and are encountered in both adults and children. Despite the wide range of surgical treatment methods available, unresolved issues remain regarding the preservation of umbilical anatomy, reduction of surgical trauma, and prevention of recurrences. In recent years, minimally invasive and organ-preserving techniques have become increasingly important in surgery, as they combine the radicality of the procedure with favorable functional and cosmetic outcomes.

Particular importance is attached to the preservation of the natural shape of the navel, since this aspect is directly associated not only with the patient's quality of life but also with their psychological and aesthetic perception of the surgical result. Therefore, the search for and implementation of new hernioplasty techniques aimed at improving cosmetic outcomes while maintaining high therapeutic effectiveness and minimizing the risk of complications is considered highly relevant.

Objective. To evaluate the effectiveness of a new surgical method for umbilical hernia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

From 2024 to 2025, 19 patients with umbilical hernia were operated on using the proposed technique (7 women and 12 men), aged 27 to 67 years. In 100% of patients, the umbilicus was preserved.

The following parameters were evaluated: duration of surgery, presence of postoperative complications, time to return to work capacity, subjective assessment of cosmetic outcome (according to the Visual Analogue Scale – VAS), recurrence during the follow-up period (up to 10 months).

Surgical steps: Skin incision. The incision is made 2.0 cm above the umbilicus along the midline of the abdomen, then curved to the left side of the umbilicus, and terminated at the level of the middle of the umbilicus (approximately 1.5 cm). This approach provides optimal access to the hernia sac and minimizes skin trauma. **Isolation of the hernia sac.** After dissecting the skin and subcutaneous tissue, the hernia sac is isolated. The upper semicircle of the umbilical ring is incised, which allows careful mobilization of the sac without damaging surrounding structures. **Opening and management of the hernia sac.** The sac is opened, and its contents (intestinal loops, omentum, etc.) are examined. If necessary, adhesions are released and non-viable tissues removed. The sac itself is treated to prevent infection and promote better healing. **Placement of the first plastic suture.** The first suture is placed on the upper semicircle of the umbilical ring: on the left lateral surface, the needle is introduced from outside to inside and back from inside to outside, 0.5 cm from the cut edge. The procedure is repeated on the right lateral surface in the same way. When tied, the umbilical ring is reinforced without damaging the umbilical cord (important for preserving blood supply and innervation). **Placement of the second plastic suture.** The second suture is placed similarly to the first: on the left lateral surface of the ring, from outside to inside and back, 0.5 cm from the edge, then continued on the right side. When tied, the ring is additionally reinforced, while maintaining the integrity of the umbilical cord. **Reinforcing interrupted sutures.** After placing the plastic sutures, additional interrupted sutures are applied to the aponeurosis outside the umbilical ring. This provides strength and reliability of the restored anterior abdominal wall. **Closure of subcutaneous tissue and skin.** The subcutaneous tissue is closed with interrupted sutures to reduce dead space and prevent hematomas or seromas. The skin is closed with cosmetic sutures, promoting aesthetic healing and minimizing scarring.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean duration of surgery was **32 ± 6 minutes**. No early postoperative complications were recorded. The average hospital stay was **2.3 days**. All patients

reported a high cosmetic outcome (VAS – Visual Analogue Scale): **8–10 points**. During the follow-up period (up to 10 months), **no recurrences** were detected.

Comparison with previously known surgical techniques (Mayo, Sapezhko, Lexer, mesh repair): The proposed method differs from standard techniques (Sapezhko, Mayo) by reduced trauma and the ability to preserve anatomically important structures. Refusal to remove the umbilicus prevents disruption of the fixation between the skin and subcutaneous tissue, which may reduce the risk of postoperative tissue sagging and cosmetic defects. This technique is particularly valuable for patients with comorbidities and those undergoing simultaneous surgeries, where minimizing operative trauma is essential.

Advantages of the proposed method:

Criterion	Khudenov’s Method	Mayo, Sapezhko, Lexer	Mesh Repair (open, laparoscopic)
Preservation of the umbilicus	Yes	Not always	Yes
Surgical trauma	Low	Moderate	Low–moderate
Cosmetic outcome	High	Moderate	High
Duration of surgery	Short	Moderate	Longer
Use of synthetic materials	No	No	Yes

The umbilicus and the round ligament of the liver are not removed or separated from the skin, which preserves the natural support of the skin and subcutaneous tissue and prevents downward displacement. **Cosmetic outcome:** Due to careful incision and delicate closure, the natural appearance of the anterior abdominal wall is preserved, which is important for patient satisfaction. **Low invasiveness and quick execution:** The surgery is less traumatic compared with classical techniques and requires less time, thereby reducing the risk of postoperative complications.

CONCLUSION

The author’s method of hernioplasty for umbilical hernia: is **minimally invasive** and **organ-preserving**, ensures high reliability of umbilical ring repair, allows preservation of cosmetic appearance and anatomical structures of the umbilical region, may be recommended as a **method of choice** in patients with comorbidities and during simultaneous operations.

Description of the Hernioplasty Technique for Umbilical Hernia with Preservation of Umbilical Anatomy According to H.Yu. Khudenov

1 – пупок; 2 – кожа; 3 – подкожная жировая клетчатка; 4 – передняя стенка влагалища *m. recti abdominis*; 5 – *m. obliquus externus abdominis*; 6 – *m. obliquus internus abdominis*; 7 – *m. transversus abdominis*; 8 – fascia transversalis; 9 – предбрюшинная клетчатка; 10 – париетальная брюшина; 11 – *m. rectus abdominis*; 12 – задняя стенка влагалища *m. recti abdominis*; 13 – *vv. parumbilicales*; 14 – апоневроз *m. obliqui interni abdominis*; 15 – апоневроз *m. transversi abdominis*; 16 – апоневроз *m. obliqui externi abdominis*.

Fig. 1. Structure of the anterior abdominal wall at the level of the umbilicus.

Рис. 2. Пупочная грыжа

Fig. 3. Umbilical hernia.

Open surgical procedures:

Stage I.Fig.

4. Incisions for umbilical hernia: 1 – midline abdominal incision; 2 – circumferential incision; 3 – semilunar incision.

For umbilical hernia, a longitudinal skin incision is made along the midline of the abdomen a few centimeters above the umbilicus, curving to the left, and continuing 3–4 cm below it. In obese patients, a semilunar or oval incision, encircling the hernia protrusion inferiorly, is more commonly used. The skin and subcutaneous tissue are dissected down to the aponeurosis of the linea alba. By mobilizing the skin flap from left to right, the skin with subcutaneous tissue is separated from the hernia sac. The sac is isolated until the hernia ring, formed by the dense aponeurotic margin of the umbilical ring, becomes clearly visible.

Stage II.

A grooved probe is introduced between the neck of the hernia sac and the umbilical ring, along which the ring is incised transversely or along the linea alba upward and downward. The hernia sac is completely isolated, opened, its contents reduced, excised, and the peritoneum closed with a continuous catgut suture.

Stage III.

Mayo plasty is performed when the umbilical ring has been incised transversely. U-shaped sutures are applied. The upper aponeurotic flap is pierced with silk from outside to inside, 1.5 cm from the edge; then, using the same thread, a stitch is made on the lower aponeurotic edge from outside to inside and from inside to outside, only 0.5 cm from its margin, exiting at the upper edge at the same level. Typically, 3 sutures are applied: one central and two lateral. When tied, the lower aponeurotic edge is placed beneath the upper one and fixed in the form of a duplication. The free edge of the upper aponeurotic flap is then sutured to the surface of the lower flap with separate interrupted sutures (second row of sutures).

Fig. 5. Mayo plasty.

Sapezhko plasty is performed when the umbilical ring has been incised longitudinally. Using Kocher clamps, the assistant retracts the left edge of the aponeurosis and bends it to maximally evert its inner surface. The surgeon then approximates and sutures the right edge of the aponeurosis to it with separate interrupted or U-shaped silk sutures, trying to advance it as far as possible. The free left edge of the aponeurosis is placed over the right one and fixed with separate sutures. This creates an aponeurotic duplication of the abdominal wall.

Proposed Surgical Method

Fig. 6. Appearance of the umbilicus with hernia before surgery.

Fig. 7. Stage I. Skin incision starting 2.0 cm above the umbilicus along the midline, curving to the left of the umbilicus down to its midpoint (approximately 1.5 cm).

Fig. 8. Stage II. Isolation of the hernia sac with incision of the upper semicircle of the umbilical ring.

Fig. 9. Stage II – continuation. Opening of the hernia sac and management of its contents, treatment of the hernia sac.

Fig. 10. Stage III. Placement of the first reinforcing suture on the upper semicircle of the umbilical ring (first, on the left lateral surface of the umbilical ring, a

non-absorbable suture is passed from outside to inside and from inside to outside, 0.5 cm from the cut edge; then, using the same thread, the suture is continued on the right lateral surface of the umbilical ring, with the needle inserted 0.5 cm from the cut edge from outside to inside and from inside to outside, exiting on the right lateral surface). When tied, the umbilical ring is reinforced without damaging the umbilicus or the round ligament of the liver.

Fig. 11. Stage III – continuation. Placement of the second reinforcing suture on the upper semicircle of the umbilical ring (first, on the left lateral surface of the umbilical ring, a non-absorbable suture is passed from outside to inside and from inside to outside, 0.5 cm from the cut edge; then, using the same thread, the suture is continued on the right lateral surface of the umbilical ring, with the needle inserted 0.5 cm from the cut edge from outside to inside and from inside to outside, exiting on the right lateral surface). When tied, the umbilical ring is reinforced without damaging the umbilicus or the round ligament of the liver.

Fig. 12. Stage III – continuation. Placement of interrupted sutures on the edges of the aponeurotic wound outside the umbilical ring.

Fig. 13. Stage IV. Interrupted sutures on the subcutaneous tissue.

Fig. 16. Postoperative view of the umbilical region.

Stages of the Operation

1. Skin incision – A longitudinal incision is made 2.0 cm above the umbilicus along the midline, curving to the left of the umbilicus down to its midpoint (approximately 1.5 cm).
2. Isolation of the hernia sac – The hernia sac is mobilized with incision of the upper semicircle of the umbilical ring.
3. Opening and management of the hernia sac – The sac is opened, its contents treated (examination, reduction, removal of non-viable tissue if necessary), and the sac itself is processed.

4. Placement of the first plastic suture on the upper semicircle of the umbilical ring – On the left lateral surface, the needle is inserted from outside to inside and back from inside to outside, 0.5 cm from the cut edge; the same suture is then continued on the right lateral surface, with the needle inserted 0.5 cm from the cut edge from outside to inside and from inside to outside, exiting on the right side. When tied, the umbilical ring is reinforced without damaging the umbilical cord.

5. Placement of the second plastic suture on the upper semicircle of the umbilical ring – Technique is identical to the first suture (left side: outside–inside, inside–outside, 0.5 cm from the cut edge; continued to the right side with the same measurements). When tied, the umbilical ring is reinforced again without injury to the umbilical cord.

6. Placement of additional reinforcing interrupted sutures – Applied to the edges of the aponeurotic wound outside the umbilical ring.

7. Closure of subcutaneous tissue and skin – Interrupted sutures are placed on the subcutaneous tissue, followed by cosmetic sutures on the skin.

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